

THE USE OF ULTRAFILTRATION IN THE EXTRACTION OF TRITERPENE SAPONINS CONTAINED IN HERNIARIA GLABRA PLANT

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Relevance: Today, the purification and standardization of biologically active substances extracted from medicinal plants is a pressing issue. Traditional methods often involve a lot of time and the use of additional chemicals, which can be harmful to the environment. The ultrafiltration method, however, offers a more environmentally friendly and energy-efficient alternative. Triterpene saponins, found in the *Herniaria glabra* plant, are important pharmacologically active compounds. By using this method, it is possible to effectively concentrate and purify the saponin content of the extract, removing high molecular mass substances. This lays the foundation for producing high-quality, standardized products.

Objective: The *Herniaria glabra* plant, harvested from the Fergana Valley, is used to produce products with increased yield and high quality. This is achieved by extracting triterpene saponins from the ground top of the plant using ultrafiltration.

Materials and Methods: The *Herniaria glabra* plant, which was harvested from the Fergana Valley, was dried at room temperature without exposure to sunlight. Ultrafiltration was then used to extract triterpene saponins from the dried tops of the *Herniaria* plants. Various factors affecting this process were studied in order to optimize the extraction process.

Results: Quantitative analysis of the chemical composition of *Herniaria glabra* revealed the presence of triterpene saponins at a concentration of 16.5%, flavonoids ranging from 0.3% to 0.7%, and phenolic acids ranging from 0.3% to 1.0%. The plant also contains iridoids at a concentration of 1.2%, as well as tannins, polysaccharides, and mineral salts. During the extraction process, plant raw materials release large amounts of primary and secondary metabolites. This can make it difficult to purify triterpenes. To address this, an ultrapure filtration method was used. To do this, 1,000 grams of dried *Herniaria glabra* plant were extracted four times with hydromodule using 70% ethanol at a ratio of 1:12. Then, an ultrafiltration technique was applied to purify the primary metabolites. The process involved extracting 1 kg of the dried plant four times using the hydromodulator with 70% ethanol at the same ratio. After the extraction, the resulting extract was diluted and the amount of triterpene saponin was quantified using spectrophotometry. The extract contained 1.35% of the total volume in 12 liters. Optimal conditions for the alcohol extract ultrafiltration process were then studied. According to the study, under optimal conditions, triterpene saponins in the extract were found to pass through 95% of the filtrate at a rate of 10 kDa. The rate of movement of these triterpenes through the membrane was 200 L/s, and the temperature was 60°C. The passage rate of triterpenes was 15 L/S, and the saponin content in the extracted sample was 2.8%. These results led to a two-fold increase in the concentration of saponins after purification from substances with molecular weights greater than 10kDa. Currently, work is ongoing to purify saponins from other metabolites.

Conclusions: Triterpene saponins were found to be as high as 16.5% in the *Herniaria glabra* plant, and the ultrafiltration method effectively concentrated them. Under optimal conditions (10 kDa

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membrane, 60 °C, 200 l/s flow rate), 95% of the saponin passed through the filtrate, leading to an increase in the triterpenoid saponin content from 1.35% to 2.8% in the extract.